

Notes

Stable Complexes of Oxochromium(v)

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A large number of complexes of oxomolybdenum(v) are known¹⁻⁵. The complexes of oxochromium(v) are unstable and sensitive to moisture though a few dioxochromium(v) complexes⁶ and some metal salts of $[\text{CrOCl}_2]^{2-}$ are known⁶. We report here the preparation and characterisation of stable compounds of oxochromium(v) with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole.

Experimental

2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazole (PBZ) was prepared as reported earlier⁷.

$(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_2]$: CrO_3 (~2 g) was dissolved in cold ($<0^\circ$) concentrated HCl (0-50 ml) and treated with ice-cold concentrated HCl solution of 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (3.8 g in 100 ml) with stirring. A reddish brown crystalline solid separated slowly. It was filtered, washed with ice-cold HCl and dried over P_2O_5 .

$[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$: $(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_2]$ (~3.0 g) was suspended in dry dichloroethane (50 ml) and refluxed at $40-50^\circ$ for 2 h. The resulting solid was washed with dry ether and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

The electronic reflectance and ir spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were recorded as reported earlier⁷. The oxidation state of chromium in the complexes was determined iodometrically and was found to be 4.95 ± 0.10 . The analytical and physical data of complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The complexes $\text{PBZH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_2]$ and $[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$ are stable at room temperature in dry air but converted to bluish green product in moisture. $(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_2]$ is soluble in methanol and DMF while $[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$ has poor solubility in methanol but dissolves appreciably in DMF. The solutions of the complexes disproportionate or decompose slowly. The room temperature magnetic moment of $\text{PBZH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_2]$ is 1.70 B.M. and that of $[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$ 1.72 B.M., indicating the presence of one unpaired electron in these complexes. The reflectance spectrum of $(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_2]$ displays weak and broad bands at 22 500, 18 650 and 12 820 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3A_1$, ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3B_1$ and ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3E_1$ transitions respectively in distorted octahedral field⁸. The reflectance spectrum of $[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$ displays weak and broad bands at 18 870 and 13 800 cm^{-1} and a shoulder at 24 100 cm^{-1} attributed to *d-d* transitions similar to those found in oxomolybdenum(v) and oxochromium(v) complexes⁸. The electronic band positions of the complex $[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$ are observed at higher energy than that of the parent salt $(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_2]$. The ir spectra of $(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_2]$ and $[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$ display $\nu_{\text{Cr}=\text{O}}$ as a strong band at 948 and 962 cm^{-1} respectively. The pyridine ring breathing mode of PBZ (996 cm^{-1}) in the complex $[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$ shifted to higher frequency and observed at 1 012 cm^{-1} in the complex $[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$ but retained at the same frequency in $(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_2]$. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band of benzimidazole moiety (1 638 cm^{-1}) shifted to lower frequency (at 1 612 cm^{-1}) indicating the coordination of ligand through $\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N}$ nitrogens^{9,10} in $[\text{CrO}(\text{PBZ})\text{Cl}_2]$. In case of $(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_2]$, the $\nu_{\text{O}=\text{N}}$ band is not affected appreciably. The NH stretching mode of PBZ (3 247 cm^{-1}) is raised to higher frequency by 25 cm^{-1} in the pentachloro salt $(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_5]$ indicating protonation of NH group. In case of $[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$, the NH stretch is not affected appreciably indicating

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis : % Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff}^* B.M.	$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{**}$ cm^{-1}
	Cr	N	Cl		
$[\text{CrOCl}_2(\text{PBZ})]$	14.24 (14.06)	11.36 (11.66)	28.38 (28.79)	1.72	22 500s 18 650br 12 820br
$(\text{PBZH}_2)[\text{CrOCl}_2]$	11.31 (11.74)	9.28 (9.49)	40.56 (40.04)	1.70	24 100s 18 870br 13 800br

*At 304 K, **s - strong, br - broad.

that the benzimidazole NH is not involved in coordination.

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**Thermodynamic Study of Complexation of
2-Hydroxy- and 2,4-Dihydroxy-deoxybenzoins
with Iron(III), Copper(II), Zinc(II)
and Cadmium(II)**

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THE present paper describes a thermodynamic study on the complexation of 2-hydroxydeoxybenzoin (2-HDB) and 2,4-dihydroxydeoxybenzoin (2,4-DHDB) with Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}. Stability constants were determined by Calvin-Bjerrum's titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of extra pure (E. Merck) or A.R. grade. The ligands 2-HDB and 2,4-DHDB were prepared and purified by standard procedures^{2,3}. Equilibrium studies were conducted (298 K) at four different ionic strengths (NaClO₄) 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 mol dm⁻³ and those for the 2-HDB system (293 and 303 K) and for the 2,4-DHDB system (303 and 308 K) were conducted at an ionic strength of 0.10 dm⁻³. Dioxane-water (1:1, v/v) was used as solvent for the 2-HDB systems and ethanol-water (1:1, v/v) for the 2,4-

DHDB systems, and solvent corrections⁴ were made. Temperature was maintained within ± 0.02 K in a MLW (West Germany) NBE type thermostat. The pH measurements were made with a Radiometer PHM 26 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.005 pH-unit).

Results and Discussion

Titration of only one of the two ionisable protons in 2,4-DHDB could be observed at the given experimental conditions. The pH range of complexation with Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were 2.5–3.1, 4.2–6.3, 5.1–6.6 and 6.7–8.4 for 2-HDB and 2.5–3.4, 4.2–6.4, 5.5–7.5 and 6.5–8.4 for 2,4-DHDB respectively.

The $\bar{n}_H$ values lay between zero and one. Beyond the upper pH limits given above, wide divergence from the normal titration curves occurred due to partial hydrolysis of the complexes. Calculations of $\bar{n}$ and pL were, therefore, done upto the upper pH limits only. The values of $\bar{n}$ before hydrolysis set in, lay between zero and one and as a consequence only the 1:1 metal–ligand complexes have been reported. The experiments were repeated for two different metal–ligand molar ratios and the results were found to be similar which proved the non-formation of polynuclear complexes.

The log K_H and log K values at different ionic strengths⁵ are reported in Table 1. Table 2 incorporates the log K_H and log K values at different temperatures at 0.10 M (NaClO₄) and other thermodynamic parameters. Stabilities of the complexes are

TABLE 1—log K_H AND log K VALUES* OF 2-HYDROXY- AND 2,4-DIHYDROXYDEOXYBENZOIN COMPLEXES** AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTH (I)

Ligand	Cations	log K_H /log K				
		$I = 0.05$	0.1	0.15	0.20	0.00
2-HDB	H	11.84	11.76	11.65	11.63	12.07
	Fe ^{III}	11.88	11.74	11.56	11.52	12.26
	Cu ^{II}	9.15	8.95	8.81	8.68	9.61
	Zn ^{II}	8.10	7.93	7.79	7.68	8.54
	Cd ^{II}	6.56	6.42	6.34	6.21	6.88
2,4-DHDB	H	8.16	8.14	8.13	8.12	8.20
	Fe ^{III}	8.03	7.90	7.80	7.73	8.35
	Cu ^{II}	5.27	5.15	5.03	4.94	5.60
	Zn ^{II}	3.78	3.61	3.53	3.42	4.20
	Cd ^{II}	3.35	3.23	3.14	3.10	3.60

*Limits of error = ± 0.01 – 0.03 in log scale. **At 298 K.

found to decrease with the increasing ionic strength. The thermodynamic stability constants (log K_o) (Table 1) have been obtained by extrapolation of log K vs $\sqrt{I}$ plots to zero ionic strength. The order, Fe^{III} > Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II} of stabilities is in agreement with that of Irving and Williams⁶ and Mellor and Maley⁷. Negative values of free energy (ΔG) indicate that the formation of these complexes

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